

**SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF KEY
CHALLENGES IN INDIA AND IRAN**

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Abstract

The purpose of this Study is finding Sustainable Tourism Development tourist business activities can have considerable impact on local development trends. The local impacts of the tourism industry are diverse and are often unique to the tourism sector.

'Sustainable Tourism' is a frequently quoted. It is usually presented in strategies and plans prepared at different levels, but it is also used in everyday life besides professional and academic circles. As the fundamental document of Iran and India's Tourism planning, the National Tourism Development Strategy claims: 'The Sustainable utilization of the natural and cultural attractions is highly important for tourism; in the utilization of resources are irreversible negative processes must be prevented. (National Tourism Development Strategy, 2005, p.20).

After the concept of Sustainable Tourism was defined, it revised from time to time. In addition, the demand for measuring the impacts and changes of tourism received more emphasis in the last decade. The above mentioned strategy also states that 'presently' Sustainable Tourism is only a theoretical concept in both countries (Iran and India). In spite of different initiatives the
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indicator system suitable for the verification of the Sustainable Operation of the developments and the comprehensive regulation are missing'. (National Tourism Development Strategy, 2005, p.20). several researchers deal with creating models or systems to be used for assessing Sustainability in tourism(see e.g. Kovacs et al.,2006; Kosi-Barani,2006;David-Baros,2009), However, there is a missing link between defining the concept of Sustainable Tourism and implementing it in practice. If Sustainability is a major objective to be achieved, the Stakeholders of tourism must know the concept and principles of Sustainable Tourism, moreover they should have positive attitudes towards its practical aspects. It is especially important that the representatives of the local governments,

In this respect, we define the pathology or evaluate functions of Sustainable Tourism Development. Finally the hypotheses that Sustainable Tourism Development can play an important role in India and Iran by increasing the educational level of their managers, tour leaders and suppliers considering process and Technology factors are examined. And according to broad area, we can't access to all data.

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Introduction:

The Tourism is rapidly growing phenomena and it becomes one of the largest industries in the World. The effect of tourism is extremely varied. It plays an important and certainly positive role in the socio- economic and political development in destination countries by, creating new employment opportunities. Also, in certain instances, it can contribute to abrader cultural and understanding by creating awareness, respecting the diversity of cultures and ways of life. Different parties will have to be involved in the process of developing sustainable tourism.

What is Sustainable Tourism?

The meaning of the term 'Sustainable Tourism has been seen as a value-laden construct (Bramwell, Henry, Jackson and Van Der Straatech, 1996) and one that is open to interpretation (Butler, 1999). It is interpreted as cast multifariously, as a philosophy, as an ideology, a concept, a political catch phrase, a process or even as product (Wall,1996). Bulter argues that the key for Sustainable Tourism 'is not ensuing the continued introduction of small-scale, environmentally and culturally appropriate form of tourism, but as a activity to make

existing mass tourism developments as sustainable as is possible"(1999,p.13) Lu and Nepal (2009) document sustainable tourism's evolution in this direction, highlighting the term's shift in relevance from small-scale to mass tourism. Farrell and Twining-Ward (2004) argue that sustainable tourism should be considered in the context of a whole system, rather than being conceived solely at the destination level as an approach; now being captured in measurement of tourists' total ecological impacts (Wackernagel and Rees,1996).

As tourism is essentially an economic activity, sustainable tourism has become subsumed by the broader notion of Sustainable Development, conceived as tourism "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs"(Bramwell and Lane, 1993; World Commission on Environment and Development [WCED].1987, p. 43) It is framed by the domains of environmental integrity, social equity and economic prosperity (Bansal,2005), or as triple bottom line reporting.

Tourism in Iran

Iran , considered as among the top 10 countries in terms of cultural and historical tourism attractions , and it is defined listed as top five nations in terms of ecotourism potentials. Enjoying a rich diversity of weather conditions the north is influenced by the cold Siberian winds 40 degrees below zero, the center and east are under the influence of hot weather from Gobi and Caricum sandy regions, 60 degrees above zero. Caspian nature, the rich, humidity, vitality, green and woodlands. The Alborz nature and tends of over 4000 meters. The

Tourism in India

India is a country with a history of civilization spreading over more than 5000 years. The essences of Vedic Islamic and western cultures are all blended in India civilization. It is a multi-cultural, multi-religious, and multi-linguistic country. The cultural heritage of India has a glorious past and traditions. It was ruled by different races from time to time. Different rulers of different religious attitudes ruled on this part of land. It imbibed in itself the culture and tradition of these periods.

Its travel tradition starts with per Vedic Indus valley civilization, which flourished in the north western part of India from 3000 to

Zagros nature and unattained nature stubborn and beautiful. The Desert nature, mysterious and wonderful. Iran enjoys different and various climates almost the entire climates of the world nevertheless it also has another characteristic, old memories of an old land.in Iran there are nine reserved, 19 national parks , 19 natural monuments, 33 wildlife refuges, 95 protected areas and 22 international woodlands that are properly spread through the country.

1500 B.C. and has witnessed visits of people of different centers of human settlements for the purposes of social integrations trade and learning.

Key problems

There are many problems which are being faced by foreign tourism in India and Iran, which are discussed below:

Transportation problems

The absence of good transportation system is a big problem in the sustainable development of tourism in India and India which they are unsafe and very poor conditions and requires immediate attention. The other problems related with transportation are:

Share of Top 10 Countries of the World and India in International Tourist Arrivals in 2012

Rank	Country	International Tourist Arrivals * (in million)	Percentage (%) Share
1	France	83.0	8.02
2	USA	NA	-
3	China	57.7	5.57
4	Spain	57.7	5.57
5	Italy	46.4	4.48
6	Turkey	35.7	3.45
7	Germany	30.4	2.94
8	UK	29.3	2.83
9	Russia	25.7	2.48
10	Malaysia	25.0	2.42
	Total of Top 10 countries	390.9	37.76
	India #	6.6	0.64
	Others	637.5	61.60
	Total	1035.0	100.00

*Provisional, N.A. : Not Available

Excludes nationals of the country residing abroad.

Source: UNWTO Barometer April 2013.

Transportation problems

The absence of good transportation system is a big problem in the sustainable development of tourism in India and India which they are unsafe and very poor conditions and requires immediate attention. The other problems related with transportation are:

- (i) There is a lack of parking around the tourism attraction like historical places etc.
- (ii) Dangerous positions of many roads of India and Iran, which can cause accidents.

Lack of Tourists reception centers (TRO)

There is a lack of tourists' reception centers in India and Iran to provide the basic information about the tourist destination. The absence of this important center, leads to loss in revenue as tourists visiting India do not move to all places at tourist's attraction.

Discrimination Pricing

There is discriminating pricing for foreign tourists in most of the important monuments there is different pricing for domestic and foreign tourists.

Food service is also one of the major problems in this country. Food served is spicy and served under unclean conditions. Non available of the regional and continental dishes is also a big problem.

Visa facilities

Visa facilities are yet another problem. There is no system of single window clearance for obtaining tourist visa. Tourists visiting India has to go through various clearance system and other formalities to obtain tourist visa. This prevents them for planning their tour to India. Stringent eligibility requirements and cumbersome procedure put off many visitors from visiting India.

Other problems

1. Obsolete and non-interesting tourism itinerary that does not provide value for money.
2. Beggars are one of the main problems faced by foreign tourist and harassment by beggars is increasing day by day.
3. There has been no stoppage of theft and crime against foreign tourists.
4. Tourism policies instability
5. Lack of training of human resource development.
6. Lack of professional personnel
7. Lack of innovativeness in marketing
8. Insufficient communication with travel agencies.

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